

INTERACTIVE SOCIOCULTURAL ASSIGNMENTS FOR TRAINING STUDENTS IN INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION

Article's purpose. Considered in the article is the problem of teaching intercultural communication in the context of a professional and business spheres.

Methodology. The author substantiates the idea that the speech activity of a foreign language speaker is defined by the ethnopsychological peculiarities characteristic of a particular sociocultural environment. The author suggests that teaching intercultural communication should be organized in accordance with the indicative and performing stages. The indicative stage involves acquiring the knowledge of the ethnopsychological characteristics of the native speaker of the target language and developing the skills to navigate in a foreign language interlocutor. The aim of the performing stage is to develop the students' ability to realize effective interaction with the native speaker of the language being studied using typical behavior strategies. It is advisable to use the assignments aimed at teaching effective intercultural communication which can be used at both stages of training.

Scientific novelty. The author presents the examples of indicative and interactive tasks which can be used for teaching intercultural communication (ICC). It is noted in the article that the indicative tasks aimed at analyzing the situations of ICC can also be used as interactive tasks and involve discussion and staging of these situations of interaction between the speakers of different cultures. Special attention is paid to such a technique as cultural assimilators, the purpose of which is to teach them to consider the situations of ICC from the point of view of the speaker of a different culture and to understand a different perception of reality. Situations analyzed in cultural assimilators that can be used at indicative and performing stages. At the performing stage the task is to act out the situation in the cultural assimilator according to the relevant behavioral characteristics of the speakers of the target culture. In this case, cultural assimilators can be used as the interactive tasks.

Conclusion. A set of interactive sociocultural assignments presented in the article is suggested for training students in intercultural communication.

Key words: intercultural communication, ethnopsychological peculiarities, cultural assimilator.

In teaching intercultural communication, it is advisable to include two stages in the process of sociocultural competence formation: indicative and performing [6]. The indicative stage involves mastering the knowledge of the ethnopsychological characteristics of the native speaker of the target language and developing the skills to navigate in a foreign language interlocutor. The aim of the performing stage is to develop the students' ability to implement effective interaction with the native speaker of the language being studied using typical behavioral strategies. As the part of this stage, students in their statements representing concrete acts of communication, using tasks, should recreate a certain segment of the reality of the functioning of the studied linguistic culture, using sociocultural knowledge, skills, abilities and qualities acquired at the indicative stage. The tasks of the executive stage of the sociocultural competence (SCC) formation process are: the development of sociocultural skills to use adequate linguistic and non-linguistic means to make statements in situations of intercultural communication (ICC), vary the basic strategies of behavior; the development of communicative flexibility as a sociocultural ability; fostering sociocultural politeness as a sociocultural quality.

It should be noted that the indicative tasks aimed at analyzing the situations of ICC can also be used as interactive tasks and involve discussion and staging of these situations of interaction between speakers of different cultures.

We would like to present the examples of tasks aimed at developing skills of orientation in situations of intercultural communication in the business sphere, which can also be used as interactive tasks.

1. Analyze the causes of unsuccessful communication in problematic situations and establish what both communicators perceived as «alien». Imagine a situation of interaction between British and Thai managers to discuss this problem. An example of a problematic intercultural situation: «The British manager refused to work in Thailand, because his subordinates did not adhere to the deadlines set by themselves, and did not fulfill the obligations undertaken by themselves in drafting the contracts. All attempts to encourage employees to discipline, even at the cost of a lower pay, failed, because some of the staff after that did not come to work at all [5, 252]».

2. Analyze the photos with various communicatively significant gestures that are part of non-verbal code in different cultures. Explain the meaning of the gesture, suggest a communicative situation in which it can be used, and compare with the native culture [5, 253–254]. Act out the situations using communicatively meaningful gestures in the photos.

3. Analyze the announcements given in the same situations in one language in the American and British linguistic cultures. Explain the significance of these advertisements to the representative of the native culture on behalf of native speakers of American and British cultures.

American announcement: «Video controlled».

British culture: «In the interest of our regular customers these premises are now equipped with central security closed circuit TV» [5, 279].

4. Analyze the dialogue between the American manager and the Greek employee. Explain the meaning of their verbal behavior and what exactly they meant [8, 59]. Act out this situation.

Tasks for the analysis of communicative styles are important for teaching students of ICC in the context of the business sphere. In narrow context cultures, such as the USA and Canada, messages are direct and do not require context for description. It is extremely important for Americans in negotiations to immediately go to the core of the problem, following the principle of honesty in a communicative style. If an American partner talks with a partner who has a different communicative style, moments of misunderstanding may arise. According to the Japanese, Americans ask too many questions, while not giving the opportunity to formulate an answer [9, 76].

At the indicative and performing stages, cultural assimilators can be used, the purpose of which is to teach them to consider the situations of ICC from the point of view of the speaker of a different culture and to understand a different perception of reality. Situations analyzed in cultural assimilators can be acted out according to the necessary behavioral characteristics of the speakers of the target culture. In this case, cultural assimilators can be used as the interactive tasks.

Cultural assimilators have a certain structure and consist of the following components [9, 154–155]:

- 1) descriptions of situations in which representatives of two cultures interact;
- 2) four interpretations of their behavior;
- 3) «feedback» – highlighting the «correct» interpretation from the point of view of representatives of a different culture and the analysis of its features.

The selection of situations for the cultural assimilator occurs by interviewing representatives of other cultures who have experience in communication in the target culture. The most common situations are recorded in the form of «cultural episodes». Then, by interviewing the representatives of cultures, the most probable interpretations of the conflict are compiled, which are included in the cultural assimilator. As a result of the discussion of ready-made explanations of the causes of behavior, students should choose the most appropriate interpretation of behavior characteristic of the representatives of the target culture. Based on the discussion, you can then organize a role-playing game according to the suggested situation.

Interactive assignments (IA) suggest the direct execution of speech activity and are aimed at developing sociocultural skills to use adequate linguistic and non-linguistic means of writing statements in situations of ICC; vary the basic strategies of behavior with a representative of a foreign language linguistic culture; development of sociocultural ability of communicative flexibility; education of the sociocultural quality of sociocultural politeness.

In accordance with the degree of a student's independence in the use of linguistic material and in the choice of the content of speech, we distinguish interactive tasks of three levels. Interactive assignments of the 1st level (IA1) tightly control the trainees' speech activity, predetermining the choice and use of specific speech means and clearly determine the content of the speech utterance. Interactive assignments of the 2nd level (IA2) provide for flexible management of the students' speech activity, implemented due to the lack of a ready-made model for solving a communicative problem. Interactive assignments of the 3rd level (IA3) imply minimal control, directing the students' speech activity and limiting the area of linguistic and speech means.

The hierarchy of management provides dynamics in the development of sociocultural skills. The actions of the students are built on all the enlarging units of foreign language material and are becoming more complicated, lower-order actions are included in higher-order actions, simple in complex [5, 196]. Given internal and external circumstances stimulate the student to produce the necessary speech utterance in the context of the educational process. The assignment of the student's speech behavior is descending, i.e. the degree of their independence increases, the degree of «freedom» of their speech behavior by gradual liberation from the supports [2, 184]. When performing IA, both verbal and graphic supports are used, the sequence of which can be represented by a

movement from meaningful verbal supports to semantic supports and to the absence of supports. IA1 involves the use of meaningful verbal supports in the form of «language capsules» or language tools in the instructions for tasks that govern both the choice of language tools and the choice of the content of a speech utterance. In IA2, semantic verbal supports are used, which determine mainly the content of a speech utterance. In case of difficulty in designing the content of the statement when performing IA2, students can use «value capsules» as a support. IA3 are performed by students without the use of any supports.

IA1 are tasks in single-role actions and are aimed at teaching reactive and initiating speech behavior. According to I. L. Bim, teaching reactive speech behavior should be slightly ahead of learning initiative speech behavior, since it is easier to respond to what is said than to generate a speech action itself [2, 182]. IA1 provide the highest degree of «compulsion» of the student in the use of language tools and in the choice of content of expression. Using these tasks, the student is forced to act in accordance with internal and external circumstances that strictly regulate his/her speech behavior. FM1 suggest the cultivation of sociocultural politeness and include tasks producing: reacting replicas; initiating replicas.

IA2 are aimed at training the organization of interaction based on micro situations and suggest a great variability of the learner in solving a communicative problem. In a problem situation, certain guidelines can be set: the subject of speech, communication partners (their status roles, psychological characteristics) and the expected pragmatic effect, the result of communication. Performing IA2, trainees act in accordance with the designated landmarks that guide their speech behavior, and fill them with appropriate speech actions. As a result of flexible management, students implement relatively independent statements. The content of a speech statement is regulated by semantic verbal supports that can partially set the content of the speech behavior of one of the communicants in a dialogue or completely determine the content of the speech behavior of both communicants using a functional dialogue scheme. As a support in the design of the content of the statement, «value capsules» can be used. IA2 suggest the development of communicative flexibility, the cultivation of sociocultural politeness and include the tasks for organizing interaction in which the content of the speech behavior of one of the communicants and the speech behavior of both communicants are specified.

In assignments for dramatizing intercultural situations, the choice of language tools, lines of speech behavior and content of speech are determined by the students themselves in accordance with the conditions of the situation. In such situations, as a rule, an episode of communication between the carriers of the studied and native linguistic cultures is presented, which is the basis for the stage performance.

Tasks for dramatizing culturally oriented role-playing games provide for alternate performance by students of social and interpersonal roles in accordance with the indicated communicative and didactic conditions in the context of the indicated MCO situation. A culture-oriented role-playing game is a «problem-communicative foreign language task that creates social speech modeling by trainees of role positions (indicated in these tasks) taking into account functional factors of foreign and MCOs, as well as the sociocultural background of role situations and prescriptions or expectations in the process of jointly solving socially and professionally significant communicative tasks» [7]. The structural components of such a game (goal of the game, content of the game, set of social roles, conditions for implementation) are formulated and presented in such a way as to orient trainees towards the culture of the country of the language being studied, immersing them in the sociocultural context of a foreign language linguoculture [7]. This content is implemented through a specific educational speech material intended for actualization during the game, and is deployed according to a certain plot. Unlike other tasks, culture-oriented role-playing games teach not only how to say, but answer the question why and why you need to say something, than create a motive for communication, providing the student with the opportunity to introduce himself as a native speaker of the language being studied and to realize and experience specific manifestations of typical EPO of the speaker of the target language in speech behavior.

IA3 are intended for training in the implementation of communicative interaction and suggest the development of the ability to vary the main strategies of communicative distance, communicative contact, communicative self-presentation, as well as the development of communicative flexibility. The tasks provide for free communication, are creative in nature and require minimal control of the students' speech activity, which is carried out from the instructions for the task – these are the tasks for implementation of interaction, to which relate the dramatization of situations of MCO and the dramatization of culturally oriented role-playing games (V. V. Safonova).

The main component of a culture-oriented role-playing game, like any role-playing game, is the role, namely, the totality of social and interpersonal roles, the performance of which by students involves them in the process of communication and communication mastery [7]. Performing various roles (status, positional, situational), the student learns to follow a specific communicative program, choose appropriate language tools, vary behavioral strategies and show communicative flexibility in order to justify the «role-based projections» of the speech behavior of the target language speaker in similar situations. In the process of fulfilling the task, the student develops sociocultural abilities and cultivates the sociocultural qualities necessary for an effective ICC. In a culture-oriented role-playing game, social relations existing in the society are reproduced, that obliges the participants to follow certain rules and conditions of the game, follow the norms of communicative foreign language behavior. The coincidence of the role precepts existing in a foreign language linguistic culture with the

role expectations of a certain speech behavior, and he is able to implement effective ICC with a native speaker of the target language.

The content of culture-oriented games is determined by both the theme of the course and a specific goal. Culture-oriented games are aimed at teaching students how to use and vary the basic behavioral strategies in which typical ethnopsychological peculiarities of the speaker of the target language are realized. So, for students to develop the ability to establish and maintain communicative contact through the use of a strategy of communicative contact, culturally-oriented role-playing games «Let us get acquainted» can be used, which include the following possible situations: two strangers (Belarusian and American) who are forced to sit at the same table in a crowded cafe, start a conversation; two passengers start and maintain a conversation on a train, bus or plane; first meeting of an American pen-friend; dating library, party, etc.

To develop the ability to create a positive microclimate of interaction using the strategy of communicative self-presentation, the cultural-oriented role-playing games «The skill of self-presentation» are effective, suggesting dramatization of such subjects as: your friend won an international competition, you express him your praise, emphasizing the positive aspects of the presentation, you convince the teacher that your thesis is worthy to take one of the prizes in the thesis competition; you are undergoing a job interview, etc.

Culture-oriented role-playing games include role-playing episodes and complex role-playing games [9, 146]. In role-playing games-episodes, several interlocutors can be involved, depicting a given situation in accordance with predefined roles. The whole group of students takes part in complex role-playing games, distributing and arranging roles at their discretion in accordance with the rules of the game.

Staging situations of ICC, playing out possible solutions to the same problem, ensures the development of socio-cultural abilities and cultivating socio-cultural qualities. Following the norms of a foreign language communicative culture in the process of communication fosters the quality of sociocultural politeness. The ability to take into account the changing conditions in the ICC situation promotes the development of students' communicative flexibility of speech behavior. Examples of discussions can be a group discussion of the values embedded in proverbs of native and foreign cultures, as well as work in groups to develop an explanation of intercultural conflict situations between the representatives of different cultures.

Thus, the organization of training for students of ICC, taking into account the indicative and performing stages, will contribute to both mastering the knowledge of the ethnopsychological peculiarities of native speakers of the target language and developing the skills, abilities and qualities that ensure effective interaction.

References

1. Бим И. Л. Методика обучения иностранным языкам как наука и проблемы школьного учебника. М. : «Русский язык», 1977. 240 с.
Vim, I. L. (1977). Metodika obuchenija inostrannym jazykam kak nauka i problemy shkol'nogo uchebnika [Methods of teaching foreign languages as a science and the problems of a school text-book]. M., «Russkij jazyk».
2. Бим И. Л. Теория и практика обучения немецкому языку в средней школе: проблемы и перспективы: учеб. пособие. М.: Просвещение, 1988. 256 с.
Vim, I. L. (1988). Teorija i praktika obuchenija nemeckomu jazyku v srednej shkole: problemy i perspektivy [Theory and practice of teaching German in secondary school: problems and prospects]: ucheb. posobie. M.: Prosveshhenie.
3. Китайгородская Г. А. Методические основы интенсивного обучения иностранным языкам. М.: Моск. ун-т, 1986. 175 с.
Kitajgorodskaja, G. A. (1986). Metodicheskie osnovy intensivnogo obuchenija inostrannym jazykam [Methodological foundations of intensive teaching of foreign languages]. M.: Mosk. un-t.
4. Лебедько М. Г. Культурные преграды: преодоление трудностей в межкультурном общении. Владивосток: Дальневост. ун-т, 1999. 196 с.
Lebed'ko, M. G. (1999). Kul'turnye pregrady: preodolenie trudnostej v mezhkul'turnom obshhenii [Cultural barriers: overcoming difficulties in intercultural communication]. Vladivostok: Dal'nevost. un-t.
5. Молчанова Г. Г. Когнитивная поликодовость межкультурной коммуникации: вербалика и невербалика: учебник. М.: ОЛМА Медиа групп, 2014. 208 с.
Molchanova, G. G. (2014). Kognitivnaja polikodovost' mezhkul'turnoj kommunikacii: verbalika i neverbalika [Cognitive polycoding of intercultural communication: verbal and non-verbal]: uchebnik. M.: OLMA Media Grupp.
6. Починок Т. В. Формирование у студентов языкового вуза социокультурной компетенции: диссертация кандидата педагогических наук: 13.00.02. Гомель, 2012. 300 л.
Pochinok, T. V. (2012). Formirovanie u studentov jazykovogo vuza sociokul'turnoj kompetencii [Formation of sociocultural competence in linguistic university students]: Candidate's thesis. Gomel: Francisk Scorina Gomel' State University. Gomel'.

7. Сафонова В. В. Социокультурный подход к обучению иностранному языку как специальности: диссертация доктора педагогических наук: 13.00.02 М., 1992. 528 л.
Safonova, V. V. (1992). Sociokul'turnyj podhod k obucheniju inostrannomu jazyku kak special'nosti [Sociocultural approach to teaching a foreign language as a specialty]. Doctor's thesis.
8. Стефаненко Т. Г. Этнопсихология. М.: ИП РАН, Академич. проект; Екатеринбург: Деловая книга, 2000. 320 с.
Stefanenko, T. G. (2000). Jethnopsihologija [Ethnopsychology]. M.: IP RAN, Akademich. proekt; Ekaterinburg: Delovaja kniga.
9. Рот Ю., Коптельцева Г. Встречи на грани культур: игры и упражнения для межкультурного обучения. Калуга: ООО «Полиграф-Информ», 2001. 188 с.
Rot, Ju., Kopteltseva, G. (2001). Vstrechi na grani kul'tur: igry i uprazhnenija dlja mezhkul'turnogo obuchenija [Meetings on the Edge of Cultures: Games and Exercises for Intercultural Education]. Kaluga: ООО «Poligraf-Inform».

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ІНТЕРАКТИВНІ СОЦІОКУЛЬТУРНІ ЗАВДАННЯ ДЛЯ НАВЧАННЯ СТУДЕНТІВ МІЖКУЛЬТУРНОГО СПІЛКУВАННЯ

Мета. У статті розглядається проблема навчання міжкультурної комунікації в контексті професійної та ділової сфер.

Методологія. Автор обґрунтовує думку, що мовленнєва діяльність користувача іноземної мови визначається етнопсихологічними особливостями, характерними для конкретного соціокультурного середовища, та пропонує організувати навчання міжкультурної комунікації відповідно до орієнтувального і виконавського етапів. Орієнтувальний етап передбачає оволодіння знаннями етнопсихологічних характеристик носія цільової мови та формування навичок орієнтації у співрозмовникові з іноземної мови. Мета виконавського етапу – розвинути у студентів уміння здійснювати ефективну взаємодію з носіями мови, що вивчається, використовуючи типові стратегії поведінки. Пропонується застосовувати завдання для навчання ефективного міжкультурного спілкування, які можна використовувати на обох етапах навчання.

Наукова новизна. Автор наводить приклади орієнтувальних та інтерактивних завдань, якими можна скористатися для навчання міжкультурного спілкування. У статті зазначається, що орієнтувальні завдання, спрямовані на аналіз ситуацій міжкультурної комунікації, можуть також використовуватися як інтерактивні завдання та включати обговорення і відтворення цих ситуацій взаємодії між носіями різних культур. Особлива увага приділяється таким технологіям, які можуть бути використані як культурні асимілятори, мета яких – навчити розглядати ситуації міжкультурної комунікації з точки зору носія іншої культури та зрозуміти різне сприйняття дійсності. Ситуації проаналізовані в культурних асиміляторах, які можуть бути використані на етапах орієнтування та виконання. На виконавському етапі завдання полягає в тому, щоб викласти ситуацію в культурному асиміляторі відповідно до необхідних поведінкових характеристик мовців цільової культури. У цьому випадку культурні асимілятори можуть використовуватися як інтерактивні завдання.

Висновки. У статті представлений комплекс інтерактивних соціокультурних завдань для навчання міжкультурної комунікації в контексті професійної та ділової сфер.

Ключові слова: міжкультурна комунікація, етнопсихологічні особливості, орієнтувальний етап, виконавчий етап, культурний асимілятор.

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